

Procurement Policy

Procurement procedures

- (1) MIRRI-ERIC may contract by **simplified direct award**, awarding on the basis of an invoice or equivalent document, when the value of the contract does not exceed 5.000 euros, or in the case of a works contract it does not exceed 10,000 euros¹.
- (2) MIRRI-ERIC may contract by **direct award**, by invitation to tender to an entity of its choice, when the value of the contract does not exceed 20.000 euros, or in the case of a works contract when it does not exceed 30,000 euros².
- (3) In the cases previewed in previous paragraphs, if the value of the contract, or the cumulative contract price between it and the contracts of the same tender in the previous financial year, is more than 20.000 euros, the Executive Director prepares a document with a description of the contract, as well as a justification for the selected supplier, to be submitted to the AoM for approval, prior to the acquisition.
- (4) When the value of the contract exceeds the values referred to in the previous paragraphs but does not exceed 75.000 euros, or in the case of a works contract it does not exceed 150,000 euros,³ MIRRI-ERIC may contract through a **prior consultation** procedure, by inviting at least three entities of its choice to submit a tender and may negotiate with them the aspects of the performance of the contract to be concluded, or through a prior **public tender**.
- (5) When the value of the contract exceeds 75,000 euros, or in the case of a works contract when the value of the contract exceeds 150,000 euros, MIRRI-ERIC must contract through a prior public **tender**.
- (6) Regardless of the value of the contract to be concluded, MIRRI-ERIC may contract by **direct award**, by invitation to tender to an entity of its choice, in the

¹ These are the values set out in the Public Contracts Code - Article 128(1)(c) of the PPC.

² These are the values set out in the Public Contracts Code - art. 19 d) and art. 20 no. 1 d) of the PPC.

³ These are the values set out in the Public Contracts Code - art. 19 c) and 20 no. 1 c) of the PPC.

situations provided for in the Public Contracts Code, namely in articles 24 to 27a⁴.

- (1) For the purposes referred to in paragraph 5 of the previous clause, MIRRI-ERIC can use **preliminary market consultations**, **innovation partnerships** or **design contests**, as provided for in articles 35a, 218a, 219 of the PPC.
- (2) MIRRI-ERIC can also opt for a **pre-qualification procedure for candidates**, procedures for **negotiating tenders** or a **competitive dialogue**, as provided for in articles 162, 193 and 204 of the PPC.
- (3) After the approval of the annual Work Program, MIRRI-ERIC may decide to publish **pre-information notices** in the Official Journal of the European Union, indicating to potential interested parties the type and estimated value of all the contracts it intends to conclude in the following 12 months by public tender, as provided for in article 34 of the PPC.
- (4) Procedures can be conducted by a jury, composed of an odd number of members, who must sign a declaration of non-existence of conflicts of interest before the start of their duties.

Procurement documents

- (1) In the **direct award** or in the **prior consultation**, MIRRI-ERIC shall prepare and approve in advance the **call for proposals**, which shall contain the:
 - a) The technical and functional specifications of the subject of the contract to be awarded and other aspects of the performance of that contract that the tender must fulfil, such as the deadline and any basic price;
 - a) The form of the award criterion and any factors and sub-factors that specify it.
 - b) Whether the tenders submitted will be subject to negotiation and, if so, which aspects of the performance of the contract to be awarded MIRRI-ERIC is not prepared to negotiate;
- (2) In the public tender procedure, MIRRI-ERIC shall prepare, approve and disclose in advance the following **Procurement documents**.

⁴ It is intended to give MIRRI-ERIC the same contractual freedom that the PPC confers on public entities subject to it.

- c) **Contract Notice**, used as a means of calling for competition;
 - d) **Program of procedure**, specifying the rules applicable to the procedure up to the conclusion of the contract, including the award criterion and any factors and sub-factors for the evaluation of tenders, together with their respective weighting coefficients;
 - e) **Tender specifications**, which specify the characteristics and technical requirements of the object of the contract and the performance of the contract to be observed, including the basic parameters to which the tenders are bound, such as price and performance deadlines.
- (3) Contract Notice shall contain the following information:
- a) Description of the procurement: nature and extent of works, nature and quantity or value of supplies, nature and extent of services. Where the contract is divided into lots, this information shall be provided for each lot. Where appropriate, description of any options.
 - b) Estimated total order of magnitude of contract(s); where the contract is divided into lots, this information shall be provided for each lot.
 - c) Admission or prohibition of variants.
 - d) Timeframe for delivery or provision of supplies, works or services and, as far as possible, duration of the contract.
 - e) Conditions for participation and conditions to which performance of the contract is subject, if applicable.
 - f) Time limit for receipt of tenders (open procedures) or requests to participate (restricted procedures, competitive procedures with negotiation, dynamic purchasing systems, competitive dialogues, innovation partnerships).
 - g) Physical or electronic address to which tenders or requests to participate shall be transmitted.
 - h) Language or languages in which tenders or requests to participate must be drawn up.
 - i) Information whether the contract is related to a project and/or program financed by Union funds.
 - j) Type and deadlines for administrative, judicial or arbitration review procedures.

- k) the Internet address where the other parts of the procedure are available for consultation.
- (4) Procurement documents shall be made available to all interested parties free of charge by e-mail or internet address.
- (5) The notice of initiation of the procedure shall be disseminated by the following means:
 - a) On the MIRRI-ERIC website, for contracts with a value of more than EUR 5,000;
 - b) In the portuguese “*Diário da República*” (Official Gazette), in part L of the 2nd series, for contracts with a value equal to or greater than €75,000, or in the case of a works contract when the value of the contract €150,000;
 - c) In the Official Journal of the European Union, in the case of an international tendering procedure for contracts with a value equal to or greater than EUR 215,000.
- (6) Notices shall be published in the Official Gazette and in the Official Journal of the European Union by sending the notice to the Imprensa Nacional-Casa da Moeda, S.A., by electronic means, in accordance with the format and transmission methods indicated on the website of the Electronic Official Gazette.

Award criteria

- (1) In competitive procedures, the criterion for the award of the contract shall be to weigh up the value for money of the tenders, by assessing a number of factors and possible sub-factors relating to the various aspects of the performance of the contract that need to be assessed.
- (2) The lowest price criterion may only be used where price is the only relevant factor for the evaluation of tenders. MIRRI-ERIC shall promptly inform tenderers of the entity's contract award decisions and shall publish that decision on its website.
- (3) For a period of at least three years from the date it awards a contract, MIRRI-ERIC shall maintain:
 - a) the documentation and reports of tendering procedures and contract awards; and

- b) data that ensure the appropriate traceability of the conduct of covered procurement by electronic means.
- (4) On request of any Tenderer, MIRRI-ERIC shall provide promptly any information necessary to determine whether a procurement was conducted fairly, impartially and in accordance with this RoO, including information on the characteristics and relative advantages of the successful tender, except when disclosure:
 - a) would impede law enforcement;
 - b) might prejudice fair competition between suppliers;
 - c) would prejudice the legitimate commercial interests of particular persons, including the protection of intellectual property; or
 - d) would otherwise be contrary to the public interest.

Contract

- (1) Unless it does not exceed € 10,000⁵, the contract shall be in writing and MIRRI-ERIC shall notify the successful tenderer of the respective draft contract⁶.
- (2) The contract must be signed within 30 days from the date of acceptance of the draft by the parties, with preference being given to signing by electronic means.
- (3) If it is necessary to perform the contract immediately, the reduction in writing may take place after the commencement of the contractual services, provided that it is duly justified.
- (4) The award shall lapse if, for reasons attributable to the contractor, the successful tenderer fails to send the electronically signed contract within the time limit set by the body responsible for the decision to contract;

⁵ If the contract is not in writing, the contract is deemed to be the result of the combination of the invoice/invitation or tender specifications with the content of the tender awarded.

⁶ Value set out in art. 95.^o of the Public Contracts Code.